

Supplementary figure 1 ACPA fine-specificity levels in anti-CCP2-negative RA and controls.

ACPA levels for nineteen individual ACPA fine-specificities are shown in separate graphs with AU (arbitrary units) values on the Y-axes. Only ACPA levels above cutoff for positivity are shown. Horizontal lines indicate median for the group (n = 1 - 7 controls and n = 19 - 92 anti-CCP2-negative RA patients). Differences in ACPA levels between ACPA-positive anti-CCP2-negative RA patients and controls did not reach statistical significance.